

THEORY AND PRACTICE OF PROGRAMMING ON THE NEUROPEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: This article is the result of scientific research in the field of neuropsychology and neuropsychology, the study of pedagogical and psychological processes from the point of view of neurological changes occurring in the human brain, that is, the synergism of neurology with pedagogy and psychology - in 1997 as a separate discipline ideas about neurolinguistic programming and its practice, which emerged as a result of the emergence and further formation of knowledge related to the educational process of the individual, subject and person, are presented.

Keywords: neurolinguistic programming, technique, linguistics, lexicon, consciousness, intuition, communication, approach.

Introduction: If we translate neuro-linguistic programming into our language, the words "nerve language" and "programming" are derived. Or, to put it in plain language, it means programming a person using language and words.

Today, hypnotists and people who have learned manipulative techniques are using neuro-linguistic programming to achieve their goals. Below are some of the amazing techniques of neuro-linguistic programming.

ADJUSTMENT AND CONTROL TECHNIQUES

This technique can be called the basis of NLP. Because with its help, you have the opportunity to influence a person as you wish, and you can control his behavior. This technique is also the basis of hypnosis. In order to manage another person, it is necessary to adapt to him first. To adapt, you need to get into the rhythm of your interlocutor's movements. It can be his position, his gaze, holding his body, the position of his hands, the position of his legs, the rhythm of breathing, etc. But the most important thing is to get into his mood. Adapting to the rhythm of breathing gives great results. You observe your interlocutor's breathing and remain silent when

he breathes in, and speak when he breathes out. As a result, in his subconscious mind, your words will leave an impression as if they were being spoken by him.

Let's say that your interlocutor is getting angry and is puffing up like a deflated balloon. Your goal is to get rid of his anger and calm him down. In this case, you will also speed up your psyche and enter a physiological state, just like when you are angry. This will be your adaptation to the interlocutor. In this case, you will continue the conversation with him and during the conversation you will gradually break your psyche. When you become calm, you will see that your interlocutor has also calmed down.

If your interlocutor has a serious face, you will also become serious and after a while you will start to smile. Your interlocutor will follow you and start smiling. With this method, you can create any mood you want in any person. The most important thing is that you can copy the mood of your interlocutor in yourself. My little nephew likes to do the opposite of all the commands given to him. That is why it is very difficult to put him to sleep. As soon as they tell him to sleep, his sleep disappears. At that moment, I start talking to him and synchronize mine with his breathing. After we talk a little bit, I start to slow down my breathing and at the same time my speaking speed slows down. After talking about other topics for a while, I yawn and say that I am sleepy. Then he starts yawning too. I continue to brake and after a while he falls asleep. Thus, the process of putting the child to sleep does not take more than 4-5 minutes.

TECHNIQUE OF RANDOM SELECTION

If you can use this technique, your lover will always be happy. Its main purpose is to give your interlocutor a choice. But this choice is a false choice. Let him choose only one of the options you offer, or let both options give the same result. For example, your interlocutor must sign a document. Do you agree to sign it? - if you ask, he will definitely refuse and will find a thousand excuses for not doing so. Do you sign it - with a ballpoint pen or a ballpoint pen? - you can choose. Now he begins to think not about whether to sign or not, but about which pen to sign. You want to sell your product to someone, but the customer has no intention of buying it. You ask him which color you should wrap. This will change the customer's opinion about whether to buy or not. You can come up with such fake selection options as you wish based on the circumstances.

Conclusion: *In conclusion, the possibilities of neuropedagogy can be effectively used in the creation of an innovative educational environment - in the creation of its integrative theoretical base, general methodology, and specific diagnostic and correctional technologies. This helps the students not only to remember, but also to understand and understand and master the information given in the educational process without difficulty.*

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